

Modification of the simulation code BLonD for lepton rings

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Abstract

BLonD is a macroparticle simulation code developed at CERN for longitudinal beam dynamics studies, which has been extensively used for hadron synchrotrons. This Note describes the new features included in BLonD to incorporate synchrotron radiation and quantum excitation effects, which enables the use of the code for stability studies in lepton rings. Examples of the application to the FCC-ee case are also presented.

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1 Introduction

The BLoND code [1] is a macroparticle tracking code developed at CERN to simulate longitudinal beam dynamics in synchrotrons. It is developed in Python and C++ following a modular approach. There are currently modules available to simulate RF manipulations with multiple RF systems, impedance effects for single and multi-bunch cases, RF feedback loops, and injection of RF noise.

This Note describes the latest development: a new module to compute synchrotron radiation effects, including quantum excitation, to allow accurate simulations of lepton or very high energy hadron synchrotrons.

2 Synchrotron radiation module

The module has been implemented by adding three extra terms to the energy equation (see e.g. [2]):

$$\Delta E[n+1] = \Delta E'[n] - U_0 - \frac{2}{\tau_z} \Delta E'[n] + \frac{2\sigma_{\Delta E}}{\sqrt{\tau_z}} E_s r, \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta E[n+1]$ is the energy coordinate after applying the synchrotron radiation terms and $\Delta E'[n]$ is the result of the energy kick equation.

The first extra term in Eq. (1) accounts for the average energy loss per particle over one turn, which is calculated as

$$U_0 = C_\gamma E_s^4 \frac{I_2}{2\pi} \quad (2)$$

where E_s is the synchronous energy, C_γ is a physical constant given by

$$C_\gamma = \frac{1}{e^2 3 \varepsilon_0 E_0^4}, \quad (3)$$

e is the elementary charge, ε_0 is the vacuum permittivity, E_0 is the rest mass of the particle, and I_2 is the second synchrotron radiation integral, calculated over the ring as

$$I_2 = \oint \frac{1}{\rho^2} ds, \quad (4)$$

where ρ is the bending radius.

The second term in Eq. (1) describes the synchrotron radiation damping due to the difference in energy loss for each particle. The parameter τ_z is the damping time and it can be found as

$$\tau_z = \frac{2 E_s T_{\text{rev}}}{j_z U_0}, \quad (5)$$

where T_{rev} is the revolution period and j_z is the longitudinal damping partition number, given by

$$j_z = 2 + \frac{I_2}{I_4}, \quad (6)$$

and I_4 is the fourth synchrotron radiation integral:

$$I_4 = \oint \frac{\eta_x}{\rho} \left(\frac{1}{\rho^2} + 2k_1 \right) ds, \quad (7)$$

where η_x is the horizontal dispersion, $k_1 = \frac{e}{P_s} \frac{\delta B_y}{\delta x}$, P_s is the synchronous momentum, and B_y is vertical component of the magnetic field.

The last term in Eq. (1) simulate the quantum excitation. The parameter r is a random number with a Gaussian distribution with average 0 and variance 1, and $\sigma_{\Delta E}$ is the equilibrium energy spread:

$$\sigma_{\Delta E} = \sqrt{\frac{C_q \gamma^2 I_3}{j_z I_2}}, \quad (8)$$

where I_3 is the third synchrotron radiation integral:

$$I_3 = \oint \frac{1}{|\rho^3|} ds, \quad (9)$$

C_q is the quantum constant that can be found as

$$C_q = \frac{55}{32\sqrt{3}} \frac{\hbar}{m c}, \quad (10)$$

\hbar is the reduced Planck constant, m is the particle mass, and c is the speed of light.

In this implementation, it is assumed an isomagnetic guide field (all dipole magnets with the same magnetic field), and therefore the synchrotron radiation integrals (I_2 , I_3 , and I_4) can be written as

$$I_2 = \frac{2\pi}{\rho}, \quad (11)$$

$$I_3 = \frac{2\pi}{\rho^2}, \quad (12)$$

$$I_4 = \frac{2\pi R \alpha_c}{\rho^2}, \quad (13)$$

where R is the machine radius and α_c is the momentum compaction factor of the lattice.

3 Implementation details

The module gives the possibility to be used with multiple RF stations, applying the synchrotron radiation effects after each section. Also, it allows to divide each ring section in a number of parts of equal distance and apply one kick per subdivision.

The module has a Python and a C++ implementation for both the synchrotron radiation damping and quantum excitation effects, with the latter being more optimized and faster in most of the cases. The C++ implementation of the synchrotron radiation damping is also optimized for parallel computing, while the quantum excitation part does not benefit from parallel computing because the random number generation is not parallel. Two C++ implementations of the quantum excitation are available, one using the standard C++ libraries and the other one using the boost library. The latest version of the boost library (1.61.0 at the time of writing) gives much better performance than using the standard C++ library and it is therefore the recommended version if available.

4 Usage

To use the synchrotron radiation module in a BLoND simulation, one first needs to instantiate a `SynchrotronRadiation` object. If multiple RF sections are used, one `SynchrotronRadiation` object must be instantiated for each `RingAndRFSection` object. An example would be:

```
SR = SynchrotronRadiation(general_parameters, RF_section_parameters,
                          beam, bending_radius)
```

where `general_parameters` is the `GeneralParameters` object, `RF_section_parameters` is an `RFSectionParameters` object, `beam` is the `Beam` object, and `bending_radius` is the bending radius of the dipole magnets.

Other arguments that the `SynchrotronRadiation` object can take at the initialization are:

- `n_kicks`: number of kicks in which the synchrotron radiation effects are applied to take into account the continuous nature of the process. The default is 1.
- `quantum_excitation`: if True (default), it will compute the quantum excitation term in Eq. (1), otherwise it will only calculate the average energy loss and the synchrotron radiation damping term.

- python: if True, it will use the Python implementation, otherwise it will use the C++ implementation (faster, default).

After instantiating the `SynchrotronRadiation` objects, one can use the following method to print relevant parameters related to synchrotron radiation:

```
SR.print_SR_params()
```

An example of the output of this method is shown in the next section.

Finally, during the tracking the method `track()` must be called after the longitudinal tracker, as shown here:

```
SR.track()
```

If multiple RF sections are used, one needs to call the `track()` method of each `SynchrotronRadiation` object after calling the `track()` method of their corresponding `RingAndRFSection` object.

4.1 Examples

In this section usage examples of the code are shown for a practical case: the FCC-ee. In this case, the 175 GeV energy version is chosen, which is the one with the strongest synchrotron radiation effects. The machine parameters can be found in [3]. For these parameters, the output of the `SR.print_SR_params()` method is the following:

```
----- Synchrotron radiation parameters -----
jz = 2.00001013
Energy loss per RF section = 3.7713 GeV/section
Energy loss per turn = 7.5426 GeV/turn
Damping time = 23.2015 turns
Equilibrium energy spread = 0.1429% (250.1226 MeV)
-----
```

Simulations were performed using 10^6 particles and without intensity effects. The first example is shown in Fig. 1, and it shows the bunch length (4σ) evolution (blue line) under the influence of synchrotron radiation damping (no quantum excitation). An exponential fit (dashed black line) gives a damping time of 23.19 turns, which is very close to the theoretical value (23.2 turns).

Fig. 1: Bunch length calculated from simulations using BLoND (blue line) showing the synchrotron radiation damping effect. An exponential fit (dashed black line) gives a damping time of 23.19 turns. Example for FCC-ee at 175 GeV and an RF voltage of 10 GV.

The second example, presented in Fig. 2, shows the combined effect of synchrotron radiation damping and quantum excitation. On the left plot, one can see the energy spread (σ) decreasing at the beginning due to the synchrotron radiation damping term, and then stabilizes due to the quantum excitation term. The equilibrium energy spread is 254.739 MeV, close to the estimated value (250.1 MeV).

On the right plot, the bunch length (4σ) evolution is shown. Similarly to the energy spread, the bunch length first shrinks due to the damping term and then it stabilizes at around 28.647 ps. The calculated equilibrium value is 28.4 ps.

Fig. 2: Energy spread (σ , left) and bunch length (4σ , right) simulated using BLoND with synchrotron radiation damping and quantum excitation. Example for FCC-ee at 175 GeV and an RF voltage of 10 GV.

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6 References

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